

ICO: long-term success factors

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Analysis of 50+ completed ICO client projects, including the following critical components:

- White Paper Development;
- Technological Validation from Architectural and Development perspectives;
- Ecosystem Design and Governance;
- Business Model Tokenization;
- Scalability;
- Blockchain/DLT Platform/Dapp development

2. Aim

To share best industry practices and help blockchain startups learn from experiences of other companies.

3. Material and methods

The presentation is an industry analysis based on 50+ critical reviews and advisory projects completed for ICO clients.

4. Conclusions

More than 90% of ICO projects are not adequately prepared to hold their ICO and have very low probability to succeed as companies in the future.

February 4, 2018

Author biography

Mukhtar Mussabetov Mukhtar is a Founder & CEO of BlockSpace Labs Inc., a co-founder of 3 blockchain startups and a blockchain/Dapp development and advisory firm. He is a serial entrepreneur and has an extensive experience in:

- founding and launching several successful hi-tech startups;
- developing corporate governance systems for financial institutions to meet IPO requirements at major stock exchanges;
- investment management, including negotiating economic and financial conditions of 20+ world-class, multi-billion deals in oil&gas and mining industries;
- serving in senior and executive positions at multinational corporations; and
- advising corporations on business strategy and BPM.

February 4, 2018